

TIKTOK CONTENT CREATOR'S PERCEPTION ABOUT THE U.S. TIKTOK BAN**Agyapong A Evans**

Independent Researcher, University of Colorado, Boulder

ABSTRACT

This study explores how TikTok content creators perceive and respond to the proposed U.S. TikTok ban. While government narratives frame the platform as a national security risk due to its foreign ownership, creators view the ban through economic, political, and expressive lenses. Using a qualitative approach, I analyzed 25 TikTok videos tagged with #USTikTokBan, selected from over 1,600 posts. Thematic analysis revealed three key patterns in creators' narratives: (1) platform dependency and economic vulnerability, as many rely on TikTok for income and entrepreneurship; (2) algorithmic ownership and governance concerns, reflecting skepticism about data security claims; and (3) freedom of speech and information influence, where creators argue the ban limits their agency and silences independent voices. These findings suggest that the TikTok ban debate is not only about national security but also about power, visibility, and the precarious nature of digital labor in platform economies.

Keywords:

Platform Governance, Digital Labor, Algorithmic Visibility, Social Media Regulation, Tiktok

INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

Societies around the world keep evolving, especially in this digitalized era. Social media platforms today are not just technical infrastructures; they also serve as spaces where interactions, expressions, and commerce take place (Gillespie, 2010). Gillespie argues that the term 'platform' has shifted from traditional computational and architectural meanings to focus on political and social dimensions. Similarly, van Dijck et al. (2018) posit that our political and cultural activities have increasingly been configured into a platformed global ecosystem. Also, Zeng and Kaye (2022) argue that how platforms govern and how they are governed raises a lot of concern in relation to the vast political and societal impacts that come with it. Zeng and Kaye establish that, aside from dominant platforms like Facebook, Twitter, and Google, TikTok, as an emerging short video platform, has come under much scrutiny regarding governance. Currently, TikTok has about 1.8 billion active users in 2023, with the majority of its users being Millennials and Gen Z (Scatton, 2023). The U.S. alone has over 170 million active users. TikTok's emergence has come under criticism from many nations. The platform has been sued (Ridley, 2021), banned (Ellis-Peterson, 2020), and forced to sell (Allyn, 2020) in most countries where it has gained much dominance and international markets. The issue of geopolitics and the fact that ByteDance has its establishment in China raises some of these controversies with the U.S. government. Allyn (2023) highlights that despite the control of China over its companies and interests, there has been no concrete evidence of American users' data theft by China. Also, China claims to have never requested the personal data of Americans from TikTok (Juned et al., 2023). Zeng and Kaye (2022) argue that TikTok's failure to govern the kinds of content shared on the platform has contributed to why the U.S. government wants the ban to take effect. In this study, I take a different approach to delve into what this potential ban means to content creators. India has banned TikTok and other Chinese apps after a geopolitical dispute with China. This was made possible due to section 69A of the Information Technology Act, which allows the government to block websites and apps that could threaten the country's sovereignty and security (Ministry of Electronics and IT, 2020). Moreover, in 2020, the U.S. also introduced the *No TikTok on Government Devices Act* (S. 3455), which was signed into law by President Joe Biden on the 29th of December, 2022 (Allyn, 2020). This caused many reactions, and other EU institutions also banned TikTok from official government application devices due to data privacy risks and national security concerns. In his study, Scatton (2023) analyzes the political debate between TikTok's establishment in the U.S. through the lenses of securitization and riskification. Through a qualitative content analysis of political statements and media reports he finds out that, the Chinese-based social media app, is perceived more as a risk to national security rather than a direct threat. Do content creators have similar concerns?. In this study, I examine how TikTok content creators perceive and respond to the proposed U.S.

TikTok ban, initially scheduled to take effect in January 2025. The ongoing legal proceedings surrounding the case have generated considerable uncertainty among creators whose livelihoods depend on the platform. This research explores two central questions: What are the underlying reasons driving the proposed ban, and in what ways might it affect creators' sense of agency and professional identity? Additionally, the study considers whether creators engage with broader concerns about data privacy and national security or focus primarily on the creative and economic opportunities that TikTok affords. These questions situate the discussion within the larger context of law, policy, and digital governance.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- A. What are the possible reasons for the U.S. TikTok ban, and how does it undermine content creator's agency?
- B. How do creators feel about the U.S. Tiktok ban and how will that policy impact them?

LITERATURE REVIEW

The recent TikTok ban court proceedings have raised many concerns amongst content creators, specifically those who live in the United States. Most of these creators are bothered about how the potential ban set to take effect in January has the potency of affecting their businesses. Some also perceive this as a form of government impeding their First Amendment rights. Cui (2021) examines the significant impact of social media on economic growth. He talks about how social media has transformed how modern businesses operate in our society. Before the advent of social media, reaching potential customers required a lot of work and resources; however, most social media platforms now, for instance, Facebook and TikTok, allow businesses, especially the small ones, to connect with a global audience more efficiently and cost-effectively (Cui, 2021). "Through social media platforms, people can now promote products to appropriate audiences" (p. 3062). However, Rach (2021) proposes a conceptual model that examines the behavioral impact of TikTok's platform mechanics on economically driven content creators. He argues that TikTok's platform design and monetization strategies were created purposely to influence creators' behavior in ways that demand them to create content that aligns explicitly with the platform's objectives of engagement and monetization. Through qualitative interviews, he finds that economically motivated creators are more likely to adapt their content strategies to align with a platform's mechanics without being concerned about future consequences. This sometimes conflicts with intrinsically motivated creators who may prioritize personal expression over economic gain (Rach, 2021). Similarly, Gerlitz and Belmont (2013) conceptualize Facebook's *Like economy* as a paradigm that merges social engagement with economic value. They believe the Like economy idea allows these social media platforms to track and quantify user actions to generate data for businesses. By tracing the buttons and data flow of Facebook, they revealed that Facebook uses a "rhetoric of sociality and connectivity to create an infrastructure where social interactivity and user affects are instantly turned into valuable consumer data that enter multiple cycles of exchange" (p. 1349). Other scholars like Reviglio and Agustin (2020) critique algorithms' manipulative aspects that shape user autonomy. Their study traces how personalization algorithms can manipulate users into accepting these practices as beneficial. They posit that today's social media era is characterized by "an oligopolistic market in which corporate non-state actors treat users' attention as a commodity" (p. 3) in what has been described as *surveillance capitalism* (Zuboff, 2015). Just like how Reviglio and Agustin (2020) argue that social media is addictive by design, De Los Santos and Klug (2021) echo similar arguments. They trace users' awareness and perceptions of TikTok's platform privacy policy and how there is a significant trade-off between enjoying content that is personalized and protecting one's personal privacy. By conducting qualitative interviews with twelve TikTok users, they found that many of these creators felt distanced from their data, which often desensitized them to privacy concerns due to the app's complex privacy policy. To solve this problem, they suggested that there should be a need to improve the delivery of TikTok's privacy policy in order to allow users to better manage their own data. Also, Zeng and Kaye (2020) expand on this and introduce what they termed 'visibility moderation,' which goes beyond traditional content moderation but instead focuses on how platforms control the visibility and reach of user-generated content. Their study explains how TikTok's algorithm-driven decisions inadvertently marginalize certain voices.

Speaking of geopolitics, Ke (2023) shed light on Western concerns about the evolving monopoly of TikTok in the digital space. He further talks about data privacy, political influence, and child safety as the main reasons the U.S. government wants to initiate the ban. U.S. officials are concerned about how user data can be compromised and used for espionage. Ke posits that TikTok's powerful algorithm has what it takes to shape public and

political discourse, which is why it is seen as a potential threat and manipulative tool. Also, Lee and Ng (2023) discuss TikTok's Project Texas initiative to address U.S. concerns over data privacy and national security issues. As a subsidiary of the Chinese company ByteDance, TikTok has faced scrutiny from U.S. lawmakers concerned about potential foreign access to American users' data (Lee & Ng, 2023). In response, Lee and Ng highlight that the Project Texas initiative was created to reassure users that their data were safeguarded and isolated from any form of Chinese jurisdiction. Their study suggests that effective data governance requires transparency, accountability, and compliance with regional regulations in order to avoid any future consequences. Moreover, Cartwright (2020) traces how the internet serves as a battleground for geopolitical power struggles. He emphasizes how state power has increasingly been exercised through the internet. He focuses on the geopolitical rivalry between tech giants Google and Huawei. He finds out that these companies are not just private entities but also play a massive role in shaping international relations and state sovereignty. Additionally, Gillespie (2010) finds out that companies strategically use the term platform to position themselves favorably among users, advertisers, and regulators. Hence, this type of framing allows them to present themselves as neutral facilitators of content; meanwhile, their platforms often impose control over what content is shared and how it is monetized.

TikTok has over a billion users across the globe; in as much as it affords creators and users the opportunity and autonomy to create businesses and educate their audience, other hidden aspects of the platform need much attention, and that could be the reason why the U.S. government wants the app banned. Just like Reviglio and Agosti (2020), who believes social media platforms are 'addictive by design' (p. 3), De Los Santos and Klug (2021) also trace users' awareness and perceptions of TikTok's platform and how there is a major trade-off between what seems and appears to be enjoying personalized content versus protecting one's personal privacy. Likewise, Ke (2023) posits that TikTok's powerful algorithm has what it takes to shape public and political discourse, which is why it is seen as a potential threat and manipulative tool to the U.S. government. The negatives associated with these platforms are countless, but should this be the reason why people should not be able to use these apps? What are the possible solutions and discussions made by governments knowing well that these apps will keep evolving? As stated in her study, Groseth (2020) highlights that the complete ban on social media applications is inherently problematic. Building on that, I seek to discuss TikTok creators' concerns about the ban since most of them think the ban is an attempt to take away their First Amendment Rights.

METHODS

To examine the impact of the potential U.S. TikTok ban, I collected and analyzed Tiktok content creator's videos about what they had to say in relation to the ban.

DATA COLLECTION

My data consists of content creators' videos uploaded on TikTok that talked about the ban. I used hashtags to identify such videos. The first was #USTikTokBan, and the second was the #TikTokban. The first one was more specific, and it produced the videos I was looking for. Moreover, because the U.S. TikTok ban is a current topic in the news, the second hashtag also produced some relevant videos, mostly from news channels, but I ended up not using them because that was not my focus. My focus was to get uploaded videos about the ban, specifically from content creators and not even users. The data gathered for each video included the video's unique URL, ID, caption text, creator's username, number of likes, and comments. From a corpus of about 1644 posts under #USTikTokBan, I was able to download and transcribe twenty-five TikTok posts. I developed multiple themes based on these videos.

DATA ANALYSIS

There are multiple ways of approaching the analysis of videos, as established in most literature. In my study, I qualitatively analyzed videos uploaded by content creators on TikTok about their opinions on the potential U.S. TikTok ban. I specifically focused on using inductive thematic analysis since it is one of the common approaches used in analyzing videos (Herrick et al., 2021; McCashin & Murphy, 2023; Braun et al., 2016; Clark & Braun, 2013), where I traced and coded the patterned meanings across the various TikTok posts. Thematic analysis reveals patterned responses in data with particular attention to meaning, explanation, and rich description (Braun & Clarke, 2006). By using and following Braun and Clarke's recursive steps for thematic analyses ranging from inductive coding to producing themes, the themes I identified were strongly linked to the data. Through an iterative process, I independently filtered out the videos that were not in English and did not

pay attention to posts from news portals. Through this, I came up with themes and similarities in the codes. Most of the videos repeated the same arguments that different creators raised, and some also expressed more than one reason for the potential ban. As a result, I reached data saturation after analyzing 25 videos. The major themes that came up were; 1. Platform dependency and its economic impact 2. Algorithmic ownership and issues of governance and policies 3. Freedom of Speech and information control.

FINDINGS

PLATFORM DEPENDENCY AND ITS ECONOMIC IMPACT

TikTok is among the most widely used social media platforms globally, with approximately 170 million users in the United States—representing nearly half of the country's population. This prominence has sparked ongoing discussions about data privacy, governance, and national security. U.S. policymakers have expressed concerns regarding how user data are managed and the potential risks such practices may pose. These discussions have contributed to recent legislative and judicial debates over TikTok's operations in the United States. In parallel, questions have also been raised about youth exposure to digital content and the ethical responsibilities of social media platforms. For many content creators, however, the potential ban has economic and professional implications. A significant number of small businesses and independent creators rely on TikTok for income generation, audience engagement, and entrepreneurship, leading to widespread anxiety about the consequences of losing access to the platform.

Vic; And this is why they say not to rely on social media as a solid source of income. I'm not sure how this ban is going to work. I'm not sure if it's going to be like how Flappy Bird was where if you already had the app on your phone you were good, but if you tried to look it up in the app store it was gone.

Vic reflects on the uncertainty surrounding her next steps. Many creators in the analyzed posts expressed similar concerns, noting that they are unsure how to adapt their work or income streams if the ban is implemented. Several creators described feeling anxious about the lack of clarity surrounding future regulations and what they might mean for their professional activities. Vic explained that while TikTok is not her sole source of income, she recognizes that many creators rely on the platform as a primary means of financial support and audience engagement.

Vic; I'm not sure what this means for other content creators who really make a good amount of money on TikTok. Luckily for me, TikTok isn't my only source of income. I do get a monthly check from the VA anyways.

But for those that really rely on TikTok to be able to help feed their families or whatever, I'm not sure what that's going to look like. It's really hard to monetize on Instagram. YouTube Shorts is also a little bit more difficult, so I don't know what's going to happen.

There is also a strong possibility that creators who rely primarily on TikTok may need to adopt new strategies by transitioning to other social media platforms and exploring their short-form video features. Many expressed feelings of anxiety and uncertainty about this shift, noting that they are less familiar with platforms such as Instagram Reels or YouTube Shorts. Additionally, several creators pointed out that the monetization structures on these alternative platforms differ significantly from TikTok's, making it more challenging to sustain comparable levels of income or engagement. Rebuilding an audience and adapting to new algorithms, they explained, would require substantial time and effort.

SunJose; You know, this thing is not looking nice to young entrepreneurs in the US because tiktok has been so helpful to some of us. Tiktok has been a source of income to many, you know. So I don't know what these guys will do

Another creator, SunJose, expressed concern that the potential ban could negatively affect individuals who have built small businesses and established steady sources of income through TikTok. He noted a sense of uncertainty among young entrepreneurs who have recently begun using the platform to grow their ventures. Similarly, Joe encouraged creators to consider diversifying their online presence by exploring additional platforms as a proactive strategy to sustain their audiences and business activities should the policy changes take effect.

Judith; So I'm going to give it to you straight. To put things very simply, Biden signed a law that would ban TikTok if it's not sold within a year. That being said, there will be no immediate disruption to TikTok at all. There's going to be a lot of back and forth. I'm sure this is going to get dragged on.

Judith expressed confidence that TikTok would continue to contest the proposed restrictions through legal channels, referencing recent reports of the company's efforts to challenge the legislation in court. She noted that many creators view the potential ban as having implications for free expression and digital entrepreneurship. In response to this uncertainty, Judith suggested two practical steps for creators: first, to remain attentive to legal

and policy developments surrounding the case; and second, to begin diversifying their content across multiple platforms. She observed that companies such as Meta and YouTube could see increased creator activity if the ban were implemented, making it advisable for creators to expand their presence beyond TikTok to maintain visibility and audience engagement.

Judith; The two things to keep in mind are the two companies that are going to benefit the most from a TikTok ban, which are YouTube and Meta. That being said, my advice would be to take advantage of the year that TikTok is still here and still post, but also focus on diversifying yourself. If you're not already, you should be at the very least posting on Instagram. But I would also start to take YouTube seriously too. And instead of freaking out over the ban or letting influencers who are just trying to get views and comments inform you, I would use this next year strategically to post more on Instagram and YouTube.

She encouraged other creators to enter what she described as their “planning era,” emphasizing the importance of intentionally developing content strategies across multiple platforms. Many creators shared feelings of apprehension, noting that uncertainty about how alternative platforms’ algorithms would promote their content had become a source of emotional stress. TikTok’s algorithm was often described as highly responsive and effective at connecting creators with audiences, enabling rapid community growth through consistent posting. Some participants also suggested that public debates surrounding the ban might be amplified and that broader social and policy issues may warrant equal attention. Overall, discussions about algorithmic design, governance, and platform policy emerged as key areas of concern among creators responding to the evolving situation.

ALGORITHMIC OWNERSHIP AND POLICY IMPLICATIONS

The TikTok case has become a focal point in discussions about how algorithmic systems intersect with governance and policy. The U.S. government has argued that transparency in algorithmic data use and content recommendation is essential for protecting users and maintaining public trust. At the same time, creators and analysts note that the debate also raises questions about the broader regulation of digital platforms, not only TikTok. Several creators in this study emphasized the importance of consistent standards across all social media companies to ensure fairness, accountability, and clarity in data management. This highlights a growing recognition that issues of platform oversight extend beyond individual apps to the wider social media ecosystem.

Nico; The US is trying to pull a major power move by banning TikTok, and it looks like they're going to go through with it. This is not a joke. TikTok allows us to see what they don't want us to see, and they don't like that.

So we're facing a ban. Let that sink in. We can't let them silence us. With my platform, I've been able to help millions of women change their lives financially, help them make more money money. Teach them how to advocate for what they're worth at work, provide them with the tools to leave abusive relationships and generational poverty, and put strategies in place so that they can be confident about their financial futures

Nico described the ongoing debate as being less about social media itself and more about questions of governance and influence. He suggested that concerns over TikTok reflect broader issues of global power dynamics and data management between nations. Nico also highlighted the educational and economic value of his content, explaining that he has been able to assist audiences in developing financial literacy and independence through his videos, skills he believes are not always emphasized in traditional educational settings.

Nico; I taught people how to buy their first home, how to make their first investment, how to pay off their student loans, even locking in their millionaire status. Creators on this app are helping people feel seen, heard, connected and not alone, and they're trying to take that from us.

Some creators expressed hope that future policy decisions might reconsider or modify the proposed ban, thereby restoring their sense of agency and stability on digital platforms. They noted that discussions surrounding TikTok have spanned multiple U.S. administrations, reflecting the platform’s ongoing position within national policy debates. Several creators also observed that political figures from different parties continue to use TikTok for communication and outreach, which they viewed as an indication of the platform’s cultural relevance. Viker commented that, in the United States, regulatory actions are typically directed toward addressing specific behaviors rather than targeting individual companies. He questioned why the same standard could not be applied more broadly across all social media platforms if the central concern relates to user safety or data protection.

Viker; In the United States of America, we don't ban specific individuals or companies. We ban bad behaviors. If there are issues with forced data transfers to foreign governments, we need to ban forced data transfers to other governments regardless of who the company is. If there's issues relating to kids using social media and getting addicted to content, we need to stop that for all forms of social media reaching those young kids and stop them

from getting addicted. But it's insane that a bunch of lobbyists for Facebook and US Silicon Valley companies are trying to just eliminate one competitor in the name of national security.

He suggested that broader factors may be shaping the policy conversation beyond what is publicly discussed. In his view, regulatory standards should be applied consistently across all platforms rather than targeting specific companies or technologies. Referencing legal discourse surrounding *TikTok v. Garland* (2024), he noted that questions about ownership, speech rights, and digital governance continue to evolve within the context of U.S. constitutional principles. He also observed that while TikTok has already been restricted on government-issued devices, ongoing policy discussions about divestment and broader market access reflect the complexity of balancing national security considerations with the rights of private enterprises and users.

Bright; So first was the ban on government electronics. No utilization of TikTok on government electronics.

Then Canada decided to join in and ban TikTok on all of their government electronic devices as well.

Additionally, about half of the United States have employed this tactic by not allowing any TikTok utilization on their government devices

Among the creators analyzed, Bright acknowledged uncertainty about the rationale behind the proposed ban but stated that, if it is genuinely intended to address national security risks, then such measures could be justified. He mentioned that he plans to transition to other platforms but, like many creators, remains uncertain about the broader implications of the policy. Discussions among creators frequently referenced issues related to data privacy, algorithmic governance, and cross-national technology relations. Many expressed concern that the debate around security and regulation could inadvertently affect their ability to share content and maintain their creative communities. Overall, the discourse among creators reflects an ongoing tension between national security priorities and the preservation of open expression within digital spaces.

NATIONAL SECURITY AND FREEDOM OF SPEECH

Some creators interpreted the proposed ban as being less about national security and more about restrictions on expression and online discourse. At the same time, congressional discussions have emphasized concerns about the platform's potential influence on young users and the spread of digital content at scale. This contrast reflects the broader debate over how to balance protection, regulation, and expression in digital environments.

Historically, the United States has upheld the principles of a free and open internet, with legal frameworks such as the First Amendment extending protections to many forms of online communication.

Nico; It's not about protecting the kids. It's not about protecting our data. It's about freedom of speech. Let me break it down for you. TikTok has allowed me to connect with over 1.5 million people and change their lives financially by teaching them the things that they should have been taught in school. It's not an accident or oversight that we weren't taught how to manage our money or that we're not taught that you have to invest if you ever want to stop working. They don't want us to know these things. They don't want us to have a narrative that they didn't supply

Nico expressed concern that policy restrictions could diminish the visibility of the communities and conversations they have built online. He emphasized that TikTok has served as a space for diverse expression, where individuals and social movements can share experiences and perspectives with broad audiences.

According to these creators, the platform has enabled users to access and circulate information that may not always receive attention through traditional media channels, thereby contributing to a wider range of public discourse.

Nico; With my platform, I've been able to help millions of women change their lives financially, help them make more money money. Teach them how to advocate for what they're worth at work, provide them with the tools to leave abusive relationships and generational poverty, and put strategies in place so that they can be confident about their financial futures. I taught people how to buy their first home, how to make their first investment, how to pay off their student loans, even locking in their millionaire status. Creators on this app are helping people feel seen, heard, connected and not alone, and they're trying to take that from us. Now, I'm not going to let this stop my mission of helping women achieve financial freedom, but it looks like I may have to continue to do this on other platforms.

The potential ban of TikTok from the U.S. market highlights the complex relationship between national security priorities and the protection of free expression. Groseth (2020) argues that regulatory decisions concerning social media platforms should carefully balance these competing considerations. To guide policymakers, she proposes a two-part cost-benefit framework that evaluates the relative impacts of national security measures and free speech protections. Her analysis suggests that if the societal benefits of preserving open expression

outweigh the potential risks associated with data or security concerns, then restrictive regulations may raise constitutional challenges under the principles of free speech.

DISCUSSION

One of the recommendations discussed in court proceedings involved the potential divestiture of TikTok's U.S. operations to domestic business owners. Some creators, such as Kerat, questioned whether such a transition would alter the platform's structure or user experience to the extent that creators might no longer find it appealing or viable. Legal analyses, including *TikTok v. Garland* (2024), have noted that a divestiture could reshape how American users interact with global audiences on a platform originally designed for cross-cultural exchange. Beyond these structural considerations, many creators expressed concern about the economic implications of a ban, noting that TikTok serves as a primary source of income and professional opportunity for small businesses and digital entrepreneurs. While some indicated plans to transition to alternative platforms, they also acknowledged challenges associated with different algorithmic systems and slower audience growth on platforms such as YouTube and Instagram.

TikTok and its parent company, ByteDance, had filed an emergency injunction requesting that the U.S. Supreme Court review the legislation seeking to restrict the platform's operations. The company argued that the proposed ban raised constitutional questions related to the First Amendment and the rights of both creators and users to express themselves online. Echoing these concerns, Nico framed the debate as one centered on freedom of speech rather than solely on data protection or youth safety. Similarly, Joy reflected on the broader policy landscape, suggesting that national attention could also be directed toward other pressing social and economic issues. Together, these perspectives illustrated how creators interpreted the TikTok case not only as a regulatory matter but also as part of a wider conversation about rights, governance, and the prioritization of public policy in the digital age. Many creators expressed uncertainty about the future, noting that even if TikTok were not immediately banned, similar restrictions could arise in the coming years. In response, several encouraged their followers to connect with them on other platforms as a precautionary measure. Berg, one of the creators, reflected on how TikTok had transformed her professional and personal trajectory. She explained that after leaving a previous job, her content went viral, allowing her to earn between \$2,000 and \$4,000 monthly, enough to sustain her living expenses. Beyond the financial stability, she credited the platform for helping her secure opportunities in journalism, travel, and storytelling. Berg described the potential loss of TikTok as deeply unsettling, emphasizing that its removal would affect not only creators but also audiences who had built meaningful communities through the app.

A report by Oxford Economics (2023) estimated that small and medium-sized businesses contributed approximately \$24.2 billion to the U.S. economy through advertising and commercial activity on TikTok. Furthermore, about 40 percent of these businesses reported that the platform was essential to their operations (Cross, 2024). Beyond financial concerns, many creators expressed apprehension about losing their creative communities, the platform's distinctive production tools, and the cultural spaces they had built over time. The prospect of losing large followings and rebuilding audiences on unfamiliar platforms was described as both professionally and emotionally challenging. Several creators also noted that content creation served as a personal outlet for stress relief and social connection, suggesting that the ban could have broader implications for their mental well-being as well as their livelihoods.

Mike; The TikTok ban may not be about national security, but rather control over independent information. With TikTok empowering grassroots movements and real time info sharing, some speculate the US wants users back on more regulated platforms, ensuring control over narratives and reducing the influence of voices, challenging mainstream perspectives.

Many creators expressed that TikTok had provided them with a platform to educate audiences, share diverse perspectives, and amplify underrepresented voices. They viewed the potential ban as a development that could restrict these opportunities for expression and community engagement. The primary concerns raised by creators centered on the potential loss of income, creative visibility, and autonomy within the digital environment. While legal and policy discussions have acknowledged the government's responsibility to address potential security risks, creators emphasized the importance of ensuring that such measures are proportionate and transparent. Uya (2024) argued that if TikTok presents significant risks, regulatory responses should be evidence-based and targeted rather than preemptive. Drawing comparisons with previous cases involving other major technology companies, some creators questioned whether consistent standards are being applied across platforms. As

IJETRM

International Journal of Engineering Technology Research & Management

(IJETRM)

<https://ijetrm.com/>

Scatton (2023) noted, earlier controversies; such as the Cambridge Analytica case raised similar issues of data privacy and influence, yet did not result in comparable regulatory outcomes.

Here's the thing. In the United States of America, we don't ban specific individuals or companies. We ban bad behaviors. If there are issues with forced data transfers to foreign governments, we need to ban forced data transfers to other governments regardless of who the company is. If there's issues relating to kids using social media and getting addicted to content, we need to stop that for all forms of social media reaching those young kids and stop them from getting addicted. But it's insane that a bunch of lobbyists for Facebook and US Silicon Valley companies are trying to just eliminate one competitor in the name of national security. Apply the same rules to everybody (Vivek).

Although TikTok had not been directly implicated in any confirmed data misuse scandals, it was nevertheless restricted on government-issued devices due to precautionary security measures. Scatton (2023) noted that while the platform may not pose an immediate or direct threat, its ownership structure and global reach have prompted heightened scrutiny within U.S. policy discussions. This reflects a broader governmental effort to ensure that data governance frameworks remain robust in the face of emerging technologies and international market dynamics. Moving forward, policymakers may need to balance these security considerations with principles of fairness, proportionality, and transparency to maintain public confidence in digital regulation.

CONCLUSION

Groseth (2020) emphasizes that a complete ban on social media platforms risks silencing significant forms of public discourse and should only be considered when national security interests cannot be safeguarded through less restrictive measures. The case of TikTok illustrates the broader challenges of governing transnational digital platforms in an era defined by data mobility and global interconnection. As Lee and Ng (2023) note, concerns over privacy, jurisdiction, and territoriality highlight the need for cooperative frameworks that balance national sovereignty with the open exchange of information. Ultimately, effective governance should neither stifle innovation nor undermine expression but instead cultivate accountability, transparency, and inclusivity within digital ecosystems. The TikTok debate serves as a reminder that protecting citizens' security and upholding their communicative rights are not mutually exclusive goals. Crafting thoughtful, proportionate regulation—rooted in evidence, equity, and dialogue—offers the most sustainable path forward for ensuring trust and resilience in the digital public sphere.

REFERENCES

- 1) Allyn, B. (2023, March 23). *TikTok CEO says company is "not an agent of China or any other country.* NPR. <https://www.npr.org/2023/03/21/1165210054/tiktok-ceo-to-lawmakersamericans-data-not-at-risk>
- 2) Allyn, B. (2020, November 13). *Trump's TikTok sell-by date extended by 15 days.* NPR. <https://www.npr.org/2020/11/13/933916944/trump-ordered-tiktok-to-be-sold-off-but-then-ignored-the-deadline>
- 3) Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77–101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>
- 4) Braun, V., Clarke, V., & Weate, P. (2016). Using thematic analysis in sport and exercise research. In B. Smith & A. C. Sparkes (Eds.), *Routledge handbook of qualitative research in sport and exercise* (pp. 213–227). New York, NY: Taylor and Francis. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315762012.ch15>
- 5) Cartwright, M. (2020). Internationalising state power through the internet: Google, Huawei and geopolitical struggle. *Internet Policy Review*, 9(3), 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.14763/2020.3.1494>
- 6) Clarke, V., & Braun, V. (2013). Teaching thematic analysis: Overcoming challenges and developing strategies for effective learning. *The Psychologist*, 26(2), 120–123.
- 7) Cross, G. (2024, December 9). *TikTok asks Supreme Court to review ban legislation, content creators react: What to know.* USA TODAY. <https://www.usatoday.com/story/tech/2024/12/09/tiktok-ban-united-states-supreme-court-social-media-app-content-creator-react-bytedance-china/76859775007/>
- 8) Cui, Z. (2021). Analysis of the Impact of Social Media on the Economy. In 2021 3rd International Conference on Economic Management and Cultural Industry (ICEMCI 2021) (pp. 3062-3066). *Atlantis Press*. DOI:10.2991/assehr.k.211209.500

IJETRM

International Journal of Engineering Technology Research & Management

(IJETRM)

<https://ijetrm.com/>

- 9) De Los Santos, M., & Klug, D. (2021). The TikTok tradeoff: Compelling algorithmic content at the expense of personal privacy. In *Proceedings of the 20th International Conference on Mobile and Ubiquitous Multimedia* (pp. 226-229). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3490632.3497864>
- 10) Ellis-Petersen, H. (2020, June 29). *India bans TikTok after Himalayan border clash with Chinese troops*. The Guardian. <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2020/jun/29/india-bans-tiktok-after-himalayan-border-clash-with-chinese-troops>
- 11) Gerlitz, C., & Helmond, A. (2013). The like economy: Social buttons and the data-intensive web. *New media & society*, 15(8), 1348-1365. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444812472322>
- 12) Gillespie, T. (2010). The politics of 'platforms'. *New media & society*, 12(3), 347-364. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444809342738>
- 13) Groseth, C. (2020). An Economic Analysis of Banning TikTok: How to Weigh the Competing Interests of National Security and Free Speech in Social Media Platforms. Available at SSRN 3750779. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3750779>
- 14) Herrick, S. S., Hallward, L., & Duncan, L. R. (2021). "This is just how I cope": An inductive thematic analysis of eating disorder recovery content created and shared on TikTok using#EDrecovery. *International journal of eating disorders*, 54(4), 516-526. <https://doi.org/10.1002/eat.23463>
- 15) Juned, M., Maryam, S., Salam, S., & Utami, R. A. A. (2023). TikTok's conflict of interest with the us government: between big data security and economics (2017-2023). *European Journal of Communication and Media Studies*, 2(4), 1-8. <https://doi.org/10.24018/ejmedia.2023.2.4.23>
- 16) Ke, W. (2023). Unraveling the TikTok Paradox: Western Concerns, Economic Implications, and Prospects. *Highlights in Business, Economics and Management*, 20, 489-495. <https://doi.org/10.54097/hbem.v20i.13015>
- 17) Lee, R. K. W., & Ng, L. H. X. (2023). TikTok's Project Texas-Social Media Data Governance Across Geopolitical Lines. *Digital Government: Research and Practice*, 4(4), 1-5. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3631616>
- 18) McCashin, D., & Murphy, C. M. (2023). Using TikTok for public and youth mental health—A systematic review and content analysis. *Clinical Child Psychology and Psychiatry*, 28(1), 279-306. <https://doi.org/10.1177/13591045221106608>
- 19) Ministry of Electronics & IT. (2020, June 29). *Government Bans 59 mobile apps which are prejudicial to sovereignty and integrity of India, defence of India, security of state and public order*. <https://pib.gov.in/PressReleaseDetailm.aspx?PRID=1635206>
- 20) Rach, M. (2021). A qualitative study on the behavioral impact of Tiktok's platform mechanics on economically driven content creators. *International Journal of Social Science and Humanity*, 11(4), 146-150. doi:10.18178/ijssh.2021.11.4.1055
- 21) Reviglio, U., & Agosti, C. (2020). Thinking outside the black-box: The case for "algorithmic sovereignty" in social media. *Social Media+ Society*, 6(2), 2056305120915613. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2056305120915613>
- 22) Ridley, K. (2021, April 21). *TikTok faces claim for billions in London child privacy lawsuit*. Reuter. <https://www.reuters.com/technology/tiktok-faces-claim-billions-london-child-privacy-lawsuit-2021-04-20/>
- 23) Scatton, S. (2023). TikTok Risk or Threat? Competing narratives about risk and threats in the US case. <https://urn.kb.se/resolve?urn=urn:nbn:se:umu:diva-214460>
- 24) Solove, D. J. (2006). A taxonomy of privacy. *U. Pa. l. Rev.*, 154, 477. https://scholarship.law.upenn.edu/penn_law_review/vol154/iss3/1
- 25) United States Department of Justice. (2024, December 6). *Justice Department Statements on U.S. Court of Appeals for the District of Columbia Circuit Ruling in TikTok, et al. v. Garland*. <https://www.justice.gov/opa/pr/justice-department-statements-us-court-appeals-district-columbia-circuit-ruling-tiktok-et-al>
- 26) Uya, F. (2024). Cybersecurity and Social Media: Does TikTok Pose Cybersecurity Risk to the United States?. Available at SSRN 4784942. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4784942>
- 27) Van Dijck, J., Poell, T., & De Waal, M. (2018). *The platform society: Public values in a connective world*. Oxford university press.

IJETRM

International Journal of Engineering Technology Research & Management (IJETRM)

<https://ijetrm.com/>

- 28) Williams, R. D. (2021). Beyond Huawei and TikTok: Untangling U.S. concerns over Chinese tech companies and digital security (Working Paper). The Penn Project on the Future of U.S.- China Relations. https://bpbusw2.wpmucdn.com/web.sas.upenn.edu/dist/b/732/files/2021/04/Robert-Williams_BeyondHuawei-and-TikTok_Updated.pdf
- 29) Zeng, J., & Kaye, D. B. V. (2022). From content moderation to visibility moderation: A case study of platform governance on TikTok. *Policy & Internet*, 14(1), 79-95. <https://doi.org/10.1002/poi3.287>
- 30) Zuboff, S. (2015). Big other: Surveillance capitalism and the prospects of an information civilization. *Journal of Information Technology*, 30(1), 75–89. <https://doi.org/10.1057/jit.2015.5>